

Cultural Legacy of Rajasthan's Marwaris: Sustainability Challenges and Eco-Friendly Initiatives for Chirawa Fresco Art and Architecture of the Dwarkadhish Temple

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Abstract:

In India, Rajasthan is truly a land of kings and queens but also prominent for monuments of worship and peace for all the religious conviction. The Temples of Rajasthan depict countless architectural establishments that focused on the seventeenth to nineteenth century. The realm of religious temples, harking back to the yester years, epitomizes the beauty of Jhunjhunu district which comes under the Shekhawati region of Rajasthan state. The Temples of Rajasthan are the existing evidence of the artist's creativity and the lifestyles of the people of Jhunjhunu. Temples of district are bejeweled with beautiful frescoes covering every inch of available space. These frescoes are mainly painted on the mythological subjects related to the ancient Hindu epics of India.

This paper explores Dwarkadhish Temple's structure and fresco art, highlighting its heritage significance and the impact of climate, resources, religion, and socio-economic factors on its design. It also examines environmental challenges to the temple's legacy and sustainable preservation efforts for its frescoes and architecture.

KEYWORDS: *Art, Dwarkadhish Temple, Environmental challenges, Fresco, Legacy.*

Introduction:

Rajasthan is not only truly a land of kings and queens, but also renowned for its frescoed monuments. Jhunjhunu, once an ancient town, now serves as the district headquarters. It is situated in the heart of the famous Shekhawati province. The name of Shekhawati comes from Rao Shekha, a Rajput Chieftain of the *Kuchhwaha* clan,

who conquered and ruled over part of the region for a period of time around the fifteen Century. After the Mughal empire declined, the descendants of the Rao Shekha began enter their domains. One of the Raisalaji received the town of Khandella and the title of the King from the Mughal emperor Akbar on his death a town Udaipurwati passed to his son Bhojraj from his descended Shardul Singh. After becoming *deewan*, Shardul Singh suppressed the revolting *Kayamkhans*. The *Kayamkhanis* had retained political dominance over certain parts of the area now better known as Shekhawati (Hooja, 2006). Shardul Singh established his ruled over the whole district and persuades merchant to make their base at Jhunjhunu.

Indeed, the town reached its peak in trade and commerce under his rule. Art and architecture also flourished under his reign. He built palaces and havelis. Besides, Shardul Singh was a man of religious bent of mind, as Singh constructed numerous temples such as Kalyan Mandir & Gopinath Mandir in Jhunjhunu district. Every location in this province narrates its own history of bravery and valor. Temples in Jhunjhunu serve as enduring evidence of artistic creativity and the lifestyle of the people of this region. These structures adorned with beautiful frescoes that cover every inch of the available space. The people here are spiritual having strong faith in God and his power. Nothing undertaken without first worshipping God. For them, the temple is a place for such worship. They build temples for their deities to worship. The rulers and devotees of Jhunjhunu constructed places of worship, ranging in size from small roadside shrines to massive and continuously expanding complexes like the Rani Sati Temple, found in the heart of the Marwari pilgrimage.

The tradition of constructing temples in Jhunjhunu is long-lived such as Bihari ji ka Mandir, Raghunath ka Bada Mandir, and the Jain Mandir, built by Thakur Shardul Singh approximately three hundred years ago. Buildings from around 250 years ago include Kalyanji ka Mandir, Radha-Krishna ka Mandir, and Dadudas Mandir. Building structures of Shekhawati region are around 200 years old include Khetri Mahal, Gopinath Mandir, Mansa Devi Mandir, and Rani-sati Mandir. The buildings are currently not well maintained and buildings will shortly deteriorate beyond repair.

Objectives:

- Identify the architecture, and fresco art in Chirawa's Dwarkadhish Temple.
- Analysis the sustainability challenges like environmental, socio-economic which are affecting the site.
- Evaluate existing condition of Frescoed walls and potential eco-friendly initiatives by Marwari trusts, locals, and agencies.
- Summarize and propose a sustainable conservation model integrating traditional knowledge and modern science.

Research Methodology: The present study adopts a blended approach combining with historical perspective of fresco art in Shekhawati region of Rajasthan, ethnographic, and conservation methods to ensure validating data.

Data Collection Methods:

Data collection for the study was multidimensional, beginning with a field survey of the Dwarkadhish Temple of Chirawa that involved architectural documentation, interviews and the detailed recording of current situation of the fresco paintings of the Dwarkadhish Temple.

Material analysis was conducted using non-destructive testing of pigments and plaster, alongside laboratory sample studies to better understand traditional lime techniques. This was supplemented by extensive archival research into temple records, the bahi-khatas of Marwari merchant families, and the municipal records of Chirawa. Finally, qualitative insights were gathered through semi-structured interviews with descendants of patron families, local priests, caretakers, and traditional artisans (Chejaras).

Scope & Limitations: Scope limited to Dwarkadhish Temple, Chirawa as a representative Marwari-patronized site. Limitations include restricted access to private family archives and lack of prior scientific data on the site.

The Location of research:

Chirawa, is a tehsil in Jhunjhunu district near Pilani in the state of Rajasthan (India).

Historical perspective of Chirawa architecture:

In Shekhawati region of Rajasthan, Chirawa located in between Bagad and Pilani. The name Chirawa was given by Chuhard Singh in 1540. It later became a popular trading town between Jhunjhunu and Loharu. The region fell under the domain of Kishan Singh, the second of five brothers, and became part of the Khetri Thikana. Bagga Singh of Khetri granted the village to his son Abhey Singh in 1788, who elevated it to the status of a town by building a mud fort. The ruins of this fort remain, surrounding the police station about 300 meters north of the Dwarkadish Temple. Under his rule and that of his son Bakhtawar Singh, the town flourished. For years, Chirawa housed mint that produced coins from both local and imported copper (Sharma G. , 2004).

The Dalmia clan, one of the wealthiest families in Chirawa, second only to the Birla's of Pilani in terms of wealth and diverse business interests, migrated from the south of Haryana around 1800. By the next century, they were set up among the region's richer Marwari families (Wacagiarg, 1982). Chirawa ranks second among Rajasthan's painted towns. The building of this province highlights the tradition of frescoes depicting a wide range of themes. Walls painted by the local Chejaras (artists) from Chirawa were extremely popular in earlier times. Some well-known names include Chatar Singh (35 years old), Maliyo Ke Bajranji (45 years), Babulal Nai (80 years), Surender Kumar Jangid (40 years old, son of Chiranjilal Jangid), Devaram, and Neelkanth Pujari ji (both 45 years old) (Parsad, 1995). A distinctive fresco style, the work of a single artist and dating from the second and third decades of the 20th century is notable. These frescoes often depict a line of soldiers or a marching band. Each figure wears a bulky uniform and turban, with their complexions shaded in more than one tone (Bajran, 2025).

Temple architecture in India, with the expansion of a square sanctum and a pillared portico appeared during the Gupta Period. There was a gradual evolution from the

flat-roofed, monolithic temples in the initial stages to the sculptured 'shikhara' in the advanced years. In the 17th and 18th centuries, Jhunjhunu temples usually followed a simple architectural pattern. These temples constructed in Indo-Persian and Nagara styles. In layout, the temple plan was a square with graduated projections on each side, forming a cruciform shape with re-entrant angles. In elevation, the shikhara (or tower) inclined inward in a convex curve, created using a series of concentric rotating squares and circles (Jain, 2019). Typically, temples were set within a small courtyard enclosed by a single-story building, often including the priest's residence. The shrine itself is surrounded by a squat shikhara. A well was always nearby—often dug just beside the outer wall of the priest's rooms—so the priest could draw water without leaving the compound.

Local individuals are deeply religious and devotees of God and goddess. The worship places are known as Temple. In India, Temple is a 'Place of Worship,' it is furthermore known as the 'House of God.' However, for Hindus, it is both and still more. People from Shekhawati have a strong spiritual side and are deeply rooted in Indian traditional wisdom. They find divinity in ordinary life by connecting devotion with practicality to visiting places like temples. The Hindu temple, from top to bottom symbolizes the various realms of the cosmic universe – the earthy (*Prithvi*), heavenly (*Svarga* in *Akasha*), and astral (*Paatala*) worlds, representing the entire existence (Gupta, 2020). The ceilings of the temples vaulted, with curved sides supporting a flat central section. These vaults are sometimes richly painted. In cruciform temples, the central ceiling would be dome, with a small vaulted three-arched chamber as a porch on each of three sides. Examples of simple rectangular temple styles are common. Opulently painted temples in Jhunjhunu include the Gopinathji Temple in Parasrampura, while others like Kalyanji ka Temple in Jhunjhunu and Gopinath Temple in Nawalgarh are more modest. The Sri Bihari Temple in Jhunjhunu, considered architecturally fine. These temples often featured frescoes and were funded by wealthy merchants of the region. (Singh, 2025)

By the nineteenth century, temple building had increasingly become the domain of wealthy Bania families. There was a shift in architectural preference toward larger and more spacious styles. In ways, the architectural designs of temples and havelis became visually similar. Construction of the Dwarkadhish Temple dates to 1910 and features brilliant red sandstone architecture. This temple was built by Seth Bhagidar Mamraj, an ancestor from the Kanniram Dalmia family. According to the current priest of the temple, there is no documentary evidence about its origins, but it believed to have belonged to the Dalmia family. Pujari of Temple said that from 17th January 1911 to 29th May 1969 Mehant Shri Bihari Das ji (Chela) (see Figure 1), Shri Seva Das ji was taking care of the temple. Later, it donated to a sadhu and became popularly known as ‘Sadhuvo Ki Gaddi.’ Today, it is commonly known as ‘Shri Raghunathji, Dwarkadishji, and Surya Bhagwanji Ka Mandir.’

Figure 1: Portrait of Mehant Shri Bihari Das, Photograph taken by the author, November 13, 2015.

The Dwarkadish temple found around 50m west of Gandhi Chowk in Chirawa, often raised well above street-level and constructed around a courtyard. Steps run up from the street to the door which pass through a *tibari* (see Figure 2), a three-arch chamber, on to the courtyard. Along with *verandah* space, usually with three openings is called *tibari* (meaning ‘three openings’) in local language. A further development of semi covered *tibari* into an enclosed large space with four walls is the *chaubara* (meaning ‘four openings’). On all sides are *tibari*, that opposite the entrance forming the porch to the shrine, painted with frescoes.

The courtyard is enclosed within a single tire of room. The flat roof projects slightly on all sides and supported by the carved stone brackets (*todis*). These often frame painted panels have protected from direct sunlight and may be the best-preserved paintings.

Figure 2: Floor plan of Dwarkadish Temple, Chirawa (Rajasthan, India) Photograph taken by the author, November 13, 2015.

Mostly temples we constructed in the Indo-Persian and Nagra Style of architecture in the Chirawa like Dwarkadish temple. The temple is lifted in a basement like Dwarkadish Temple; these hold shops and showrooms, each giving directly on to the street (see Figure 3). The roof surrounded by decorative canopies and domes, breaking the horizontal line with flamboyant shapes. The roof projects over the external walls, too, and again sustained by brackets. The courtyard enclosed within a single tire of rooms. The flat roof projects slightly on all sides and supported by the carved stone brackets (*todis*). These often frame painted panels, protected from direct sunlight, and may be the best-preserved paintings. The temple features images of gods, goddesses, and mythical beings, including hybrid creatures like half-human, half-animal or half-bird, as described in Hindu epics, Purans, and Kavyas. It also depicts the underwater world, with creatures like fish, tortoise, crocodile, and coral, symbolizing the aquatic realm. These

Figure 3: Entrance of the Dwarkadish Temple, Photograph taken by the author, November 13, 2015.

representations reflect the temple's cosmology, highlighting water as the foundation of creation and sustenance (Gupta, 2020). Therefore, In the Hindu temple one can see the representations of men, women, children, buildings, flora -fauna, incarnations of the deities and many more on the frescoed walls which constitute the earthly world. Similar subjects painted on walls of Dwarkadish temple, temples of Rajasthan reflect great architectural achievements, particularly those built between the 17th and nineteenth centuries. These religious architectures stand for the creative legacy of the region, especially in the Jhunjhunu district, which lies in the Shekhawati region of Rajasthan.

In *Figure 4*, fresco painted in the main area of the temple depicting Arjun's feat of hitting the fish's eye during Draupadi's Swayam Vara, an episode taken from the Mahabharata. Here Arjuna's painted in the center wearing red color *angarakha* and white *dhoti*, he concentrated solely on the fish's eye in the reflection.

Figure 4: Arjun's feat of hitting the fish's eye painted on the wall , Photograph taken by the author, October 24, 2025.

In the early twentieth century, temple architecture continued to follow this pattern but, as time progressed there was a return to something more akin to the 18th century design. Modern examples resemble the old plan, with a *shikhara* over the shrine. Although religious themes tend to dominate, as they do elsewhere, the frescoes in temples can be very variable time to time that is of folk tales, soldiers, train, and even British officials may join Vishnu's incarnations. Harlal and Shankar Lal Nayak were famous for constructing temples in Jhunjhunu (Sharma, 1989).

The interior has a massive courtyard beautifully painted with frescoes. There are canopies *chhatris* and cloistered verandahs in it. The foliated arch entrance is decorated with fresco paintings. The roof of the temple is decorative with carved stone panels. In the forecourt two *seths* painted, one as Mamraj Dalmia, the other as Marwari Bania painted in the style of Kalighat paintings in black. Within the left side

in the *tibari*, frescoes on the floral designs (see Figure 5) on the ceiling are fading day by day. In the Dwarkadish temple, fresco paintings showing gods and goddesses painted anywhere on the walls either upper or lower portions. However, from a practical standpoint, a temple serves as a protected cover, shielding the frescoes from the natural elements and human interference. In the front of main space where statues of deities installed, their majority of the fresco paintings painted on the imperative episodes of Mahabharata and Ramayana one by one.

Figure 5: Front view of main space where deities installed, Photograph taken by the author, November 13, 2015.

Depiction of side profile portraits along with floral harmonical motifs creates a visual symphony of semiotics. Parallely storytelling aspects containing religious narratives depicting the beliefs of the community themes like:- shiva Parvati, Radha Krishna, Ramayana, etc. not only religious the wall panel actually has a fusion of multi-dimensional integrity having cultural and social interpretations like procession proceeding with horses and palkis of elites, some elements adjourning there also predicts the strong influence or ties of community with their rituals holding past to present with ever changing modules (a group of band- walas) those leading this procession represents the contemporary attires of these peoples.

There are beautiful panels of varied variety of Gods and Goddess on the left side (lower panel) when we enter, Rama and Sita's marriage, procession of Rama's wedding beautifully painted in the panels over there. In the middle panel, scenes of Krishana with Radha and Gopis, Shiva -Parvati painted with

Figure 6: Subjects related to Ramayana is painted, Photograph taken by the author, October 24, 2025.

yellow borders, and upper panel is full of male and female portraits with round borders of floral motifs in Blue and white color.

Beside these, 52 Avatars of Raja Bali, Vishnuji and Narhad, Krishna and Arjun on *rath*, Jatayu tries to stop Ravana abducting Sita, Krishna dances on the head of Kaliya to crush his pride and Kaliya's wife beg for his mercy, Vasdev holds Krishna on his head in the basket are painted in red, indigo, ochre, maroon, yellow, black and green. On the upper panel of the parikrama door, Three panels were made, in the center panel, Seth Bhagirath Mamraji were sitting on royal chair painted in their Dhoti-Kurta and turban along with his accountant (Singh M. , 2025), in the Left and right side, two business man were standing, slightly below in right adjacent Shri Hanumanji with Gada (weapon, A symbol of his strength and power), just below him a man sitting on chair with a lotus flower and in the left side of the door ten small panels depicting Radha-Krishnaji in different postures, almost all the frescoes are vanishing only the drawings and impression of yellow color is visible little bit.

Figure 7: Frescoes painted on the Way of Parikrama, Photograph taken by the author, October 24, 2025.

In Jhujhunu region, people worship numerous gods and deities yet trust they're all footpaths to the one ultimate reality. As the local people said, "Just as rainwater from heaven flows into the ocean, prayers to various gods reach the one God," embracing an acceptance. The Caretaker (See Figure 8) Shri Mahent Babudasji (*pujari*)' of the Dwarkadish Temple of Chirawa interconnected with the ten Jewelry shops and tailors rented outside area of the

Figure 8: Temple Pujari with Researcher, Photograph, November 13, 2015.

temple and the rent received through these shops used for performing rituals and maintenance of that the Dwarkadish temple of Chirawa.

Observations and Analysis:

Ecological issues are affecting Dwarkadhish Temple's cultural heritage as its architecture and fresco paintings in Chirawa are disappearing over time, rarely retaining their original appearance. Deterioration fallouts from interactions between materials (plaster, pigments, binding medium) and external environmental factors. The fresco painting technique also plays an important role. To recognize deterioration, we must consider the construction of fresco work particularly its materials, technique, and causes of damage or fading. Factors responsible in causing damage can be considered as follows:

- Moisture is a chief threat to fresco paintings, causing damage through several sources like leakage of water, rain, and humidity. It softens plaster of the building, breaks materials, and then triggers secondary reactions such as salt crystallization and microbial growth in the plaster or walls of the temple building. Identifying the reason of moisture source is crucial for effective conservation treatment of the frescoed walls, requiring careful study and interpretation.
- In the temple, rainwater damages exposed frescoes (*see Figure 9*), causing paint loss and plaster destruction. The rainwater harms frescoed walls primarily through moisture penetration and trapped humidity. This causes the pigments to lose adhesion, resulting in peeling, cracks, blistering and unsightly stains. Direct rain and sunlight worsen the damage, especially for outdoor or secco technique frescoes. Leaks can destroy frescoes inside buildings too. In Chirawa's building, porous walls allow

Figure 9: Rainwater damages frescoes, Photograph taken by the author, October 24, 2025.

rainwater to seep in, prolonging contact with frescoed walls and accelerating deterioration of the frescoed walls and ceiling too.

- Salts are stacked overtime on Dwarkadhish Temple's frescoed walls and ceiling, causing ugly efflorescence that damages paint and plaster. It has been observed during survey that it happens in the temple and frescoed wall too. White coat appears on the walls, messing with the fresco art.
- Heat from sunlight and fire is fixed overtime to damage temple's fresco work. Ultraviolet rays lighten pigments of the frescoes, oxidize binders, and cause colour coat to crumble. Infrared radiation leads to thermal expansion, powdering, and flaking of the pigments and surface too. Cooking fires on *chulhas* release damaging fumes, covering frescoes in soot or causing color dull with darker shades.
- Dust is a major issue for Dwarkadhish Temple's frescoes, especially in Shekhawati region's dry climate. It settles, gets mud covered by moisture, and turns into stubborn dirt, obscuring the art. Deep-rooted deposits are tough to remove without damage, and they result in moisture and fungus, making the frescoes in bad condition.
- Architecture of Dwarkadhish Temple is losing their charm. Residential spaces are morphing into commercial hubs, with shops and shutters disfiguring fresco-adorned facades, hiding even damage the fresco art from view.

Fresco paintings of Dwarkadhish temple of Chirawa can deteriorate in multiple ways simultaneously, like plaster, surface and paint degradation, dust accumulation, salt deposition due to environmental factors, and soot damage. Renewing Dwarkadhish Temple's frescoed walls is crucial as it's a cultural legacy site and a living space. Unfortunately, fake fresco techniques are being used, misrepresenting traditional fresco art. Conservation and maintenance treatment requires examining key elements affecting treatment effectiveness, not essentially a complete technical study. Exploration of frescoes before conservation is necessary. The Following efforts

suggested to preserve fresco paintings and architecture in Chirawa's Dwarkadhish Temple using sustainable practices involve:

- Using natural materials: Employing traditional fresco techniques with eco-friendly materials locally available material such as lime, natural pigments (Verma, 2009), and plant-based adhesives for restoration.
- Naturally sensitive techniques: Adopting methods that minimize environmental impact, such as natural (solar) drying and scheduling renovations during dry months (like May-June, before the monsoon season) in Shekhawati region to reduce water usage.
- Local community involvement: Engaging local artisans and communities in preservation efforts, restricting commercial activities in the building of Dwarkadhish temple like opening jewelry shops and tailor shops, while promoting cultural tradition and sustainable livelihoods.
- Eco-friendly tourism: Encouraging accountable tourism practices that support preservation, safeguarding and reduce environmental strain.
- Nature awareness through education: Raising awareness about sustainable preservation practices and the importance of cultural heritage conservation of all the ancient buildings of this region.
- Regular maintenance of the Temple: Regular upkeep of the temple includes Daily cleaning and inspections, Periodic restoration and repairs, protecting fresco paintings and idols of God-Goddess from damage, ensuring sustainable practices are tracked regularly.

These initiatives aim to protect the Dwarkadhish temple's intricate frescoes and architecture while promoting environmental sustainability.

Conclusion:

The Dwarkadhish temple built around 1910, is a prominent landmark located in the main market near Gandhi Chowk in Chirawa, Jhunjhunu district, Rajasthan (India).

Architecturally, the construction signifies an amalgamation of Indo-Persian and Nagara styles, following the regional "Haveli-temple" typology where the sacred space mirrors the domestic grandeur of a impressive mansion. Since 1997, the temple has been under the continuous supervision of Shri Shri Mahent Babudasji and his family, who reside on the premises and manage its daily maintenance and regular care.

Currently, the fresco art is predominantly organized into vertical and horizontal panels, framed by ornate floral borders positioned beneath the ceiling line. Field observations indicate a significant disparity in conservation: the interior frescoes remain in relatively good condition, whereas the exterior frescoed walls have suffered extensive weathering, hence vanishing day by day.

The study utilized localized diagnostic methods, including high-intensity lighting and magnification, to assess the physical condition of the frescoed wall surfaces, plaster substrates, and pigment layers. The following deterioration composition (structure) were recognized:

- Environmental Damage: Presence of salt efflorescence, soot, smoke stains, and surface deposits on the walls of the Dwarkadish temple.
- Physical Decay: Evidence of flaking of pigments, crust formation, deep-seated stains of spit, pasting of commercial advertisement on the frescoed walls, writings on frescoed walls, etc.

These damages are intrinsically linked to the Dwarkadish temple building's historical construction materials and the specific technical vulnerabilities of traditional fresco methods.

A critical finding of this research is the erosion of intangible legacy of the Chirawa (Rajasthan). Contemporary generations of craftsmen are no longer familiar with the "wet-process" (fresco buono) techniques of their ancestors. This loss of technical knowledge has resulted in an alienation from the spiritual and representational dimensions of the fresco art form. Given the mounting environmental pressures, there is an urgent need for sustainable conservation and maintenance efforts to preserve the architectural and artistic legacy of Chirawa's Dwarkadhish Temple.

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